

Prevalence of SARS-CoV-2 variants in Prague wastewater determined by nanopore-based sequencing

Alžběta Dostálková^{a,b}, Kamila Zdeňková^{c,*}, Jana Bartáčková^d, Eliška Čermáková^c, Marina Kapisheva^b, Marco A. Lopez Marin^c, Vojtěch Kouba^d, Petr Sýkora^e, Martin Chmel^{f,g}, Oldřich Bartoš^g, Jirí Dresler^g, Kateřina Demnerová^c, Michaela Rumlová^{a,b}, Jan Bartáček^d

^a Department of Biotechnology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Czech Republic

^b National Institute of Virology and Bacteriology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Czech Republic

^c Department of Biochemistry and Microbiology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Czech Republic

^d Department of Water Technology and Environmental Engineering, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Czech Republic

^e PVK a.s., Prague Water Supply and Sewerage Company, Czech Republic

^f Department of Infectious Diseases, First Faculty of Medicine, Charles University and Military University Hospital Prague, Prague, Czech Republic

^g Military Health Institute, Military Medical Agency, Czech Republic

HIGHLIGHTS

- SARS-CoV-2 variants in Prague wastewater were detected by nanopore-based sequencing.
- Variants detected in wastewater correlated with those in clinical samples.
- SARS-CoV-2 positives in wastewater increased earlier compared to clinical samples.
- The prevalence of subvariants varied in various Prague sub-localities.
- Sequencing of sub-sewershed samples benefits epidemiological early warning systems.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The early detection of upcoming disease outbreaks is essential to avoid both health and economic damage. The last four years of COVID-19 pandemic have proven wastewater-based epidemiology is a reliable system for monitoring the spread of SARS-CoV-2, a causative agent of COVID-19, in an urban population. As this monitoring enables the identification of the prevalence of spreading variants of SARS-CoV-2, it could provide a critical tool in the fight against this viral disease. In this study, we evaluated the presence of variants and subvariants of SARS-CoV-2 in Prague wastewater using nanopore-based sequencing. During August 2021, the data clearly

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: zdenkovk@vscht.cz (K. Zdeňková).

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showed that the number of identified SARS-CoV-2 RNA copies increased in the wastewater earlier than in clinical samples indicating the upcoming wave of the Delta variant. New SARS-CoV-2 variants consistently prevailed in wastewater samples around a month after they already prevailed in clinical samples. We also analyzed wastewater samples from smaller sub-sewersheds of Prague and detected significant differences in SARS-CoV-2 lineage progression dynamics among individual localities studied, e.g., suggesting faster prevalence of new variants among the sites with highest population density and mobility.

1. Introduction

Four years ago, COVID-19 emerged in Wuhan and dramatically spread worldwide, with 773, 449, 299 confirmed cases and 6,991,842 deaths to this date according to the WHO (data to December 31, 2023 WHO). COVID-19 is caused by Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), a member of the *Coronaviridae* family, genus *Betacoronavirus*. These viruses are responsible for mammalian and human diseases, involving Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (SARS-CoV) and the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (MERS-CoV). Similarly to other coronaviruses, the SARS-CoV-2 genome is composed of one single-stranded RNA molecule enclosed in a ribonucleoprotein complex (RNP) with nucleocapsid proteins (N). The RNP is then protected by a lipid membrane containing three nested proteins: spike (S), envelope (E), and membrane (M). Apart from the nucleocapsid, the interior of the particle also contains enzymes, accessory proteins, and cofactors needed for the replication cycle.

RNA viruses are characterized by a high mutation rate that leads to the acceleration of their evolution. Compared to other RNA viruses, such as HIV-1 that mutates with a rate of 4×10^{-3} per site per year, the mutation rate of SARS-CoV-2 is lower, oscillating around 7×10^{-4} substitutions per site per year (Zanini et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2022). A high percentage of mutations are repaired due to the proofreading 3–5 exoribonuclease activity of the non-structural protein nsp 14 (Tahir, 2021). However, regardless of the proofreading, some mutations are introduced into the genome and can affect various factors of the replication cycle, such as infectivity, virulence, or the ability to escape from the host immune response. Five SARS-CoV-2 variants of concern (VOCs) had emerged from 2019 till 2022: Alpha (B.1.1.7), Beta (B.1.351), Gamma (P.1), Delta (B.1.617.2), and Omicron (B.1.1.529). Omicron has been characterized by a high number of mutations in the S protein coding region leading to the introduction of up to 40 amino acid changes. Since the S protein is crucial for the entry of target cells and also for recognition by neutralization antibodies, mutations increased transmissibility of the virus and availability of immune escape (Dejnirattisai et al., 2022; Vitiello et al., 2022; Yamasoba et al., 2022). Due to this reason, Omicron variants have been spread very quickly and since 2022, the Omicron variants and subvariants have prevailed in the population. Moreover, individuals previously infected with other SARS-CoV-2 variants can be re-infected with a new variant originating from Omicron (Fan et al., 2022; Pulliam et al., 2022). Fortunately, the severity and lethality of Omicron-derived variants is low (Pulliam et al., 2022). Nowadays, ten circulating variants originated from Omicron are reported as variants of interest (XBB.1.5, XBB.1.16, EG.5) and variants under monitoring (BA.2.75, XBB.2.3, BA.2.86, CH.1.1, XBB, XBB.1.9.1, XBB.1.9.2). Currently, the COVID-19 pandemic has generally a stable trend. On May 4, 2023, WHO Director-General determined that COVID-19 is no longer a public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC). Despite this statement, it is important to maintain monitoring of SARS-CoV-2 in the population considering the fact that SARS-CoV-2 has been still circulating in the population. Importantly, Omicron S protein can bind not only human ACE2 but also ACE2 orthologs of different animal species indicating to potential spillover to the animal and back to the human. During the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, the animal-to-human transmission was documented for hamsters causing a local outbreak in Hong Kong and also minks (Zhu et al., 2022). Therefore, a proper surveillance system is crucial to keeping

SARS-CoV-2 in the population at a low level.

As the asymptomatic positive individuals has occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic, the relevance of wastewater-based epidemiology (WBE) has increased. Due to the absence of symptoms, the SARS-CoV-2 positives have been undetected and data obtained from clinical samples have been insufficient to determine emerging outbreaks. The potential of SARS-CoV-2 monitoring in wastewater (WW) was demonstrated during the SARS-CoV-1 epidemic in 2003, in which diarrhea was one of the common symptoms (Leung et al., 2003). Seventeen years later, studies reported that also SARS-CoV-2 positive individuals can excrete viral particles via vomit, sputum, and feces (Kaafarani et al., 2020; Kitajima et al., 2020; Rabaan et al., 2020). Indeed, Medema et al. showed that SARS-CoV-2 could be successfully detected in sewage (Medema et al., 2020). Since then, hundreds of publications have continued to report the presence of SARS-CoV-2 in wastewater and demonstrate the correlation with clinical data ((Zdenkova et al., 2022); for reviews, see (Giacobbo et al., 2021; Alhama et al., 2022; Bertels et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022)). This WBE approach has been also strongly supported and enforced by the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC).

Apart from the detection and quantification of SARS-CoV-2 RNA in WW, the determination of the individual SARS-CoV-2 variants represents a cornerstone of modern WBE (Crits-Christoph et al., 2021; Fontenele et al., 2021; Izquierdo-Lara et al., 2021; Rios et al., 2021; Agrawal et al., 2022; Rainey et al., 2022; Reynolds et al., 2022). Unlike the clinical samples (Brejova et al., 2021), wastewater is a mixture of various variants excreted by up to tens of thousands individuals including those that did not appear in the official statistic. In reality, the number of positive individuals could be even higher than the official statistics documented. Interestingly, several studies documented some sequences not identified in clinical samples (Nemudryi et al., 2020; Crits-Christoph et al., 2021; Izquierdo-Lara et al., 2021; La Rosa et al., 2021; Rios et al., 2021; Wurtz et al., 2021; Wurtzer et al., 2021; Agrawal et al., 2022). Various methods have been employed for WBE (e.g. (Crits-Christoph et al., 2021; Fontenele et al., 2021; Izquierdo-Lara et al., 2021; Agrawal et al., 2022)). Although the Illumina represents a gold standard for sequencing of clinical and even wastewater samples, long hands-on time, sequence runtime and high costs disadvantage Illumina. On the other hand, nanopore-based sequencing in combination with a protocol ARTIC v3 seems to represent well suited and generally accepted methodology, especially for the SARS-CoV-2 surveillance (Quick, 2020; Izquierdo-Lara et al., 2021; Karthikeyan et al., 2022). Izquierdo-Lara et al. analyzed the wastewater samples using the nanopore-based and Illumina sequencing technologies in parallel, and they reported no significant differences in obtained results (Brejova et al., 2021; Izquierdo-Lara et al., 2021). In October 2021, the ECDC declared the obligation to monitor SARS-CoV-2 and its variants in the wastewater of cities with at least 150,000 inhabitants (ECDC, 2021). The monitoring of individual localities appears to be an efficient strategy for predicting new potential outbreaks even in the municipal districts (Ai et al., 2021; Fontenele et al., 2021; Rios et al., 2021; Amman et al., 2022; Dharmadhikari et al., 2022; Viveros et al., 2022; Agrawal et al., 2023; Goncalves-Brito et al., 2023).

In our study, we reported the SARS-CoV-2 variants and subvariants prevalence in wastewater of Prague, the capital of Czech Republic. From March 2021 until February 2022, 300 wastewater samples were collected and 80 samples were sequenced to monitor the waves of three

prevalent variants in the Czech Republic to date: Alpha (B.1.1.7.), Delta (B.1.617.2) and Omicron (B.1.1.529). To compare the representation of SARS-CoV-2 variants, samples were collected from the inlet to the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) and also from different sub-sewersheds in Prague. We observed significant divergence in SARS-CoV-2 lineage composition in the selected localities. Up-to-date, there are very few papers illustrating the geographical distribution of SARS-CoV-2 variants in wastewater with a level of geographical detail comparable to what is presented in our paper. Furthermore, this is the first work identifying distinctive SARS-CoV-2 variants in wastewater in the Czech Republic. Consequently, our manuscript plays a pivotal role in enhancing our understanding of how various SARS-CoV-2 variants have disseminated throughout the entire European region.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Collection and processing of wastewater samples

Wastewater samples collected in different sub-sewersheds in Prague representing apartment buildings (AB) (L5, L6), hospitals (H) (L7, L19), and a bus terminal (BT) (L22) were selected to cover districts with different population sizes, dynamics and connectivity (Table 1, Fig. 1). To compare the variability in the selected localities with the sample gathering WW from the large part of Prague, the inlet to the WWTP (sewer ACK conveying approx. 50% of Prague's WWTP influent) was also analyzed. In total, 300 samples were collected twice per week from March 2021 until February 2022. At the sub-sewersheds, where automatic samplers could not be installed for practical reasons, 500–1000 mL of grab samples were collected directly from the sewer into sterile polyethylene bottles and subsequently transported to the laboratory. At the inlet of the Prague WWTP, 1 L of composite 24-h samples (40 mL every 60 min) was collected and transported to the laboratory. To cover the morning peak in wastewater flow, sampling time was always between 7 and 10 a.m. at these sites. The samples were refrigerated during transport. The samples were normalized to the wastewater flow to potentially eliminate the effect of the daily fluctuations and processed as previously described (Zdenkova et al., 2022). Briefly, 40 mL of the samples were centrifuged (4600×g, 30 min, 4 °C) and the supernatant was precipitated using 25 mM polyethylene glycol 8000 (PEG, Sigma-Aldrich, UK) together with 770 mM NaCl (Penta, Czech Republic). The precipitate was pelleted (14,000×g, 30 min, 4 °C) and the pellet was resuspended in 500 µL of TRIzol™ Reagent (Invitrogen, ThermoFisher Scientific, USA). This TRIzol suspension was stored at -80 °C and RNA was extracted after thawing.

2.2. The extraction of total RNA from wastewater

To obtain maximum yield, two 500 µL volumes of TRIzol suspension were mixed together before beginning the extraction. Then, 200 µL of

Table 1
The characteristics of samples analyzed in this study.

Locality code	Type of locality	Number of registered residents	Type of sample	Number of samples
ABL5	Apartment buildings	7075	grab	47
ABL6	Apartment buildings	1153	grab	19
HL7	Hospital & Residential area	13,148	grab	49
ABL16	Apartment buildings	6457	grab	18
HL19	Hospital area	0	grab	18
BTL22	Bus Terminal	1318	grab	45
WWTP	Sewer ACK	670,840	24-h composite	104

chloroform (Penta, Czech Republic) was added to the 1 mL of TRIzol suspension (Invitrogen, ThermoFisher Scientific, USA). Total RNA was isolated using TRIzol:chloroform extraction followed by 2-propanol and ethanol precipitation according to the manufacturer's protocol. After complete drying, the pellet was resuspended in 100 µL of nuclease-free water (Top-Bio, Czech Republic). To avoid any potential degradation of RNA, samples were immediately analyzed and quantified using one-step multiplex quantitative PCR with reverse transcription (RT-qPCR).

2.3. The detection and quantification of SARS-CoV-2 RNA copies using reverse transcription multiplex quantitative PCR (RT-qPCR)

The molecular detection of SARS-CoV-2 was performed in a 7500 Real Time PCR system (Applied Biosystems, USA) using an EliZyme OneS Probe Kit (Elisabeth Pharmacon, Czechia) according to the manufacturer's protocol. Primer-probe sets were used as was described previously (Zdenkova et al., 2022): CDC_Wu_N1-F GACCCCAAAT-CAGCGAAAT, CDC_Wu_N1-R TCTGGTACTGCCAGTTGAATCTG, CDC_Wu_N1-P FAM-ACCCCGCATTACGTTTGGTGACC-BHQ1. The thermal cycling conditions were as follows: reverse transcription at 53 °C for 10 min and inactivation at 95 °C for 2 min, respectively, followed by 45 cycles of 5 s at 95 °C and 30 s at 60 °C. For fluorescence detection and data evaluation, the 7500's software version 2.0.6 was used. The EURM-019 synthetic single-stranded RNA (synthetic ssRNA) fragments of SARS-CoV-2 were used as an *in vitro* transcribed RNA standard (JRC, 2020). The positive control (synthetic ssRNA), no template control (water) and calibration curves were included in every RT-qPCR analysis. Samples were considered positive with Cq ≤ 40. As was described previously, the limit of detection was calculated as 5 copies of SARS-CoV-2 RNA in the reaction, i.e. 625 copies in 1 L of wastewater (Zdenkova et al., 2022).

2.4. The detection of mutations specific to different SARS-CoV-2 variants

RNA isolated from Prague WW samples collected from December 2021 until January 2022 was analyzed using RT-qPCR allelic discrimination assay (DIANA Biotechnologies, s. r.o.) to determine the transition point. The transition point between two dominant variants was determined as the period when the new dominant variant was more frequent than the previous one in clinical samples collected in Prague and reported in the GISAID database. The dominant variant was the one that was most represented in the population. Using one-step RT-qPCR, we detected specific mutations for the Delta variant (amino acid substitution L542R) and Omicron variant (amino acid substitution Y505H). The limit of detection for RT-qPCR allelic discrimination assay was estimated by the manufacturer detecting at least 5 copies of SARS-CoV-2 RNA in the reaction, i.e. 625 copies in 1 L of wastewater.

2.5. The determination of SARS-CoV-2 lineages

Only 80 samples with Cq ≤ 37 were used for sequencing. All sequencing runs were performed using the Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) GridIONx5 sequencing platform, which is yet the only platform which meets most of criteria to be designated as Third Generation Sequencing (Schadt et al., 2010). Libraries for ONT sequencing were prepared according to the manufacturer's guidelines for the PCR tiling of SARS-CoV-2 virus using a Ligation Sequencing Kit (SQK-LSK109) and Native Barcoding Expansion kit (EXP-NBD196). The protocol is based on nCoV-2019 sequencing ARTIC protocol v3 (Quick, 2020). The quantification of DNA was performed using a Qubit™ fluorometer device with a Qubit™ dsDNA HS Assay Kit (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). Libraries were sequenced on the ONT GridION platform using the R9.4 chemistry (Flow-Cell). Sequencing data were base-called, i.e. transmission from physical changes in the electric current signal measured by the ONT sequencing device to biologically relevant bases, using ONT Guppy v5.1.13 (high-accuracy

Fig. 1. Map of Prague illustrating the part of the Prague sewage network with trunk sewers (dark thick line) and minor sewers (blue line). The light blue area represents the sewer shed of trunk sewer ACK, the main influent to Prague's WWTP. The dark blue areas represent small selected sub-localities. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

model).

The sequencing data were processed using the ARTIC pipeline, which provides read filtering, primer sequence trimming, reference mapping and consensus construction (Artic pipeline, 2021). Consensus sequences were subject to lineage classification using the PANGOLIN pipeline (GitHub, 2022b). Furthermore, to emphasize the origin of individual samples (mixture), we utilized the Freyja software tool, which was developed in order to disentangle and evaluate such a data (Karthikeyan et al., 2022; Garcia-Pedemonte et al., 2023). The ARTIC pipeline in default mode standardizes the coverage of SARS-CoV-2 genome to $200 \times$. We tried to increase this value up to $400 \times$, which is a sequencing depth we typically achieved. But since it did not affect the results provided by the Freyja tool, we continued using the default ARTIC options. This was in the line with our goal, i.e. to document transition points between individual SARS-CoV-2 lineages.

2.6. The origin and processing of clinical data

Clinical data were obtained from the GISAID database. Each GISAID record contains the date and place of collection. Purposely, only samples that were collected from Prague in the given date were included in the graph. To calculate the prevalence of different variants, data for entire month were agglomerated. The prevalence of the different variants was then calculated as the percentage of samples containing each variant in the given month.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Quantification of SARS-CoV-2 in Prague wastewater

Samples were collected from Prague's major sewage network as well as from the defined localities (Fig. 1). SARS-CoV-2 RNA was detected and quantified using one-step RT-qPCR. Albeit, WW samples were up-concentrated prior RNA isolation, the number of SARS-CoV-2 RNA copies was low, not reaching LOD in some samples. To avoid losses of

RNA during separated reverse transcription and qPCR, SARS-CoV-2 RNA was detected and quantified using one-step RT-qPCR, which combines both steps in one reaction. Recent studies comparing one-step and two-step RT-qPCR in the detection of SARS-CoV-2 RNA in wastewater reported that one-step is significantly more sensitive than two-step RT-qPCR (Qiu et al., 2022; Raya et al., 2024). Qiu et al. even showed that one order of magnitude more diluted RNA was detected by one-step RT-qPCR compared to two-step (Qiu et al., 2022). During one-step RT-qPCR, the N gene encoding the N protein was targeted. Although the Omicron variant and its subvariants generally carry the highest number of mutations, including those within the N gene locus, Bei et al. demonstrated that the Omicron N gene represents a valid target for PCR detection (Bei Y et al., 2021). Moreover, on April 28, 2022, the region of the N gene defined by N1 primers and the probe was confirmed by FDA to be a suitable region for the detection of SARS-CoV-2 (Exact Sciences Laboratories, 2022a). The copy numbers of SARS-CoV-2 RNA detected in WW were compared with SARS-CoV-2-positive clinical samples in Prague obtained from GISAID (Fig. 2A).

The comparison of trends representing SARS-CoV-2 RNA copies in the wastewater (the black line represents the overall positive samples with $Cq \leq 40$) and in clinical samples (the grey line represents the overall positive samples obtained from GISAID), showed three different stages of the epidemic development during 2021 in Prague (Fig. 2A). In April 2021, positive cases in both wastewater and clinical samples were decreasing. However, a significant disparity between positive cases in wastewater and clinical samples became evident at the onset of May. Unfortunately, concentration of SARS-CoV-2 RNA in wastewater can be affected by factors such as weather, the composition of wastewater including disinfectants content, pH and temperature (Bivins et al., 2020; de Oliveira et al., 2021; Sala-Comorera et al., 2021; Bertels et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022; Sherchan et al., 2023). We speculate, that the almost two orders of magnitude reduction of the RNA copy number and thus also the difference between wastewater and clinical samples was caused by higher rainfall amounts in Czechia in May 2021. The average monthly total was 98 mm of precipitations which represents 142 % of

A

B

	30.11.2021	03.12.2021	07.12.2021	10.12.2021	14.12.2021	17.12.2021	21.12.2021	04.01.2022	07.01.2022
L542R	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Y505H							•	•	•

C

Fig. 2. The detection of SARS-CoV-2 and its variants in the composite samples collected at the Prague WWTP and comparison with the number of clinical cases. (A) The prevalence of the N gene of SARS-CoV-2 detected in the samples collected at the Prague WWTP. The black line shows the moving average from the individual data points. The color coding (Alpha: red dots; Delta: green dots; Omicron: blue dots) of the data points indicates the predominant variant. The grey line shows the number of positive clinical samples reported in Prague. (B) Prevalent mutations detected in samples from WWTP in the Delta (green dots) – Omicron (blue dots) transition point using discriminate qPCR. (C) The prevalent variants of SARS-CoV-2 detected in WWTP by using ONT in comparison with the variants detected in clinical samples from Prague obtained from GISAID. Note that in May and June 2021, the low quantity of SARS-CoV-2 in Prague wastewater did not allow successful nanopore sequencing. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

the standard level calculated in 1981–2010 (Institute, 2023). The trend has been reversed during August 2021 when the copy number of SARS-CoV-2 RNA dramatically increased in wastewater samples while the clinical cases increased two weeks later. In this period, the Delta wave has been coming.

3.2. Detection of prevailing variants of SARS-CoV-2 in Prague wastewater

Our study detected SARS-CoV-2 variants in wastewater by discrimination assay and sequencing and related them to clinical samples data obtained from GISAID database. Wastewater and clinical data were gathered to represent a given time period (month) of the pandemic progression.

RT-qPCR allelic discrimination assay was used to detect the Omicron variant by targeting mutation resulting amino acid substitution in the position Y505H. Our discrimination assay confirmed its presence in WW samples in the middle of December 2021 (Fig. 2B). Our data are in agreement with the data published by the Prague water supply and sewerage company (PVK, a. s.) and the company Veolia, which first reported the presence of the Omicron variant in Prague WW (Omicron potvrzen, 2022c). However, in clinical samples also from Prague, the Omicron variant had already been detected a few weeks earlier in November 2021. This delay in detecting Omicron in WW using discrimination assay corresponds to the previous study of Rasmussen et al. (2022). Despite that they targeted different mutation resulting amino acid substitution in the position K417 N, they also observed negative WW samples despite positive clinical samples (Rasmussen et al., 2022).

Sequencing using GridION device (ONT) determined the lineage composition of SARS-CoV-2 within the population over the duration of one year. Sequencing appears to be the most appropriate option to reliably detect a specific variant. A few studies reported comparisons, advantages and disadvantages of different sequencing approaches (Carbo et al., 2023; Koskela von Sydow et al., 2023). Nanopore-based sequencing allows to sequence both short and long reads of up to 2.273 Mb (Wang et al., 2021) which can be combined to provide hybrid sequencing. The length of sequenced reads enables the assembly of genomes *de novo*. Moreover, due to possibility of detecting modified bases (i.e., methylation) and sequencing RNA, nanopore-based technology is applied for the identification of RNA modifications and epitranscriptomic analysis. Despite all these applications and improving of the accuracy, the higher error rate, around 4% compared to Illumina sequencing reaching 0.1–1%, disadvantages nanopore-based technology. In our study, this technical limitation was circumvented by applying sufficient sequencing depth and the selection of appropriate bioinformatics tools (i.e. Freyja pipeline) as suggested by other authors (Barbe et al., 2022; Karthikeyan et al., 2022; Garcia-Pedemonte et al., 2023)."

In accordance with previous studies, predominant variant in wastewater samples revealed by sequencing corresponded with the predominant variant of clinical samples except of May 2021 (Fig. 2C) (Crits-Christoph et al., 2021; Fontenele et al., 2021; Izquierdo-Lara et al., 2021). In May 2021, wastewater contained predominantly Alpha variant, even though clinical samples showed both Alpha and Delta. We hypothesized that the difference of Alpha and Delta occurrence in wastewater samples might have been caused by the relatively higher severity of Delta: Delta-positive individuals were forced to be tested due to severe symptoms while wastewater represents thousands of individuals independently on symptoms. In May to June 2021, the Prague SARS-CoV-2 cases were at a minimum, so SARS-CoV-2 RNA was not detected in the WW. This reveals a limitation of WBE. In case of low number of positive cases, SARS-CoV-2 RNA was diluted and the number of copies oscillated under the limit of detection. From July to December 2021, the Delta variant and its subvariants dominated within wastewater as well as clinical samples. Omicron replaced the Delta variant at the turn of the year 2022. Interestingly, the first cases of the Omicron

variant were identified in rainfall amounts in November 2021; however, the Delta variant was suppressed one and half months later. Compared to the clinical data, the transition of the Delta to Omicron slightly lagged in WW (Fig. 2A–C), similarly as during the transition from Alpha to Delta. The Omicron variant was subsequently predominant in the population from the beginning of January 2022. Importantly, compared to clinical samples where Omicron displaced Delta rapidly in February 2022, Delta was still detectable in wastewater samples (Fig. 2C).

Due to the character of the Delta variant often resulting in severe conditions of the patients (Riediker et al., 2022), we hypothesized that the Delta variant was excreted via feces more efficiently than the Omicron variant, which typically exhibited milder symptoms (Mahase, 2022; Ren et al., 2022; Wolter et al., 2022; Prasek et al., 2023). Although the transmissibility of the Omicron variant was higher due to the efficient immune escape than the Delta variant, the severity of the illness and the viral load of the Omicron variant was lower (Sentis et al., 2022; Manathunga et al., 2023; Yadav et al., 2023). Therefore, it is highly probable that WW projected the Delta variant preferentially in the samples where the virus concentration was higher while the clinical samples already showed the upcoming Omicron wave. Several studies contradicted the correlation of COVID-19 severity with a higher amount of SARS-CoV-2 in feces. Nevertheless, these studies were published prior to the appearance of the Omicron variant and thus cannot exclude the possible difference between Delta and Omicron variants (Cerrada-Romero et al., 2022; Lavania et al., 2022). A very recent study reported increased shedding rates with Delta predominance compared to Omicron which clearly supports our hypothesis (Prasek et al., 2023).

Another explanation of this phenomenon, i.e., that despite Omicron being predominant in clinical data while the Delta variant persisted in WW, was proposed by Yaniv et al. (2022). Their model predicted the elimination of Omicron and the return of cryptically circulating Delta. Albeit, the return of Delta seems to be unlikely to date, two studies documented the presence of the Delta variant in the wastewater after Delta was outcompeted by Omicron (Westcott et al., 2022; Haver et al., 2023). Similar to our findings, their data indicated the presence of the Delta variant in specific isolated locations. The origin of these cryptic variants remains uncertain; however, long-term patients or animal reservoirs are the most likely culprits (Gregory et al., 2022). Interestingly, while Omicron-derived variants dominate in the population nowadays, the GISAID database showed a few clinical cases with the Delta variant in August 2023 and even Delta-positive wastewater sample was identified in June 2023.

Overall, both RT-qPCR allelic discrimination assay and GridION sequencing successfully detected new SARS-CoV-2 variants in wastewater, albeit around a month after these new variants prevailed in clinical samples. Of the two methods, we suggest that sequencing is more suitable for detecting mutations, especially for such rapidly mutating variants as Omicron, compared to the discrimination assay.

3.3. Analysis of variant prevalence in various sub-sewersheds of Prague

Prevalence of SARS-CoV-2 variants in several smaller sub-sewersheds (i.e. individual localities or facilities) represents a phenomenon of major importance in current WBE (Ai et al., 2021; Rios et al., 2021; Dharmadhikari et al., 2022; Rainey et al., 2022; Zdenkova et al., 2022). To compare the subvariant representation of Prague, apartment buildings (ABL5, ABL6, ABL16), a hospital area (HL7, HL19) and a bus terminal (BTL22) were selected to represent different types of locations covering a different number of residents and their mobility. Although we collected (for practical reasons) only grab samples at the sites, we reduced the variability by keeping always the same sampling time and avoiding days with high rainfall amounts. Using RT-qPCR allelic discrimination assay, we analyzed the transition point between Delta and Omicron in sub-localities (Fig. 3A). While Delta was already missing from localities ABL5 and HL7 at the beginning of January 2022, Delta persisted in localities ABL6 and BTL22. This is consistent with the

A

	08/12/2021				15/12/2021			05/01/2022			
	ABL5	ABL6	HL7	BTL22	ABL5	ABL6	HL7	ABL5	ABL6	HL7	BTL22
A570D				•							
L542R	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•		•
Y505H								•	•	•	•

B

Fig. 3. Representation of SARS-CoV-2 variants and subvariants in WW samples collected from various localities/neighborhoods of Prague. (A) Predominant mutations detected in WW samples of selected localities at the Alpha (red dots) – Delta (green dots) and Delta – Omicron (blue dots) transition point using discriminate qPCR (B) The graphs documenting the occurrence of SARS-CoV-2 subvariants in WW samples sequenced by using ONT collected in various localities of Prague compared to WWTP in the most interesting months of 2021 and 2022 that highlight the predominance of individual variants. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

fact that localities ABL5 and HL7 are the ones with the highest number of residents, enabling more efficient Omicron spread compared to ABL6 and BTL22. The same trend was reported by Rios et al. in Nice localities (Rios et al., 2021). The spread of SARS-CoV-2 with the highest efficiency was observed in the most populated localities.

To analyze the variability in the subvariants composition at individual localities, six different periods were chosen for ONT analyses to cover waves of each variant, including Alpha (B.1.1.7.; subvariants are labeled as Q), Delta (B.1.617.2; subvariants are labeled as AY) and Omicron (B.1.529; subvariants are labeled as BA) (Fig. 3B). Variants and subvariants presented in WW samples from different localities were

those with predominance higher than 0.5 % (as evaluated by the Freyja tool). Subvariants with predominance lower than 0.5 % were not included. Whereas WWTP samples mostly contained a broad mixture of several subvariants, samples collected in individual localities comprised only a specific selection of subvariants. These differences are in an agreement with previous studies that reported different proportions of various mutations in individual localities (Ai et al., 2021; Rios et al., 2021; Amman et al., 2022; Dharmadhikari et al., 2022; Goncalves-Brito et al., 2023). The beginning of January represented a transition to the Omicron variant. The Omicron subvariants distinctly dominated in localities ABL5, HL7 and BTL22, while around 30 % of the Delta variant

remained in the sparsely populated ABL6. Although BTL22 involved a similar number of residents to ABL6, BTL22 was a location with a high mobility rate, including both local as well as long-distance transportation (Rios et al., 2021). This confirmed that our methodology can differentiate particular localities with various epidemiological risks and characteristics.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alžběta Dostálková: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Kamila Zdeňková:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Jana Bartáčeková:** Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Project administration. **Eliška Čermáková:** Data curation, Formal analysis. **Marina Kapisheva:** Formal analysis, Writing – original draft. **Marco A. Lopez Marin:** Data curation, Formal analysis. **Vojtěch Kouba:** W. **Petr Sýkora:** Data curation, Funding acquisition. **Martin Chmel:** Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Oldřich Bartoš:** Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Jiří Dresler:** Funding acquisition, Project administration. **Kateřina Demnerová:** Funding acquisition, Resources. **Michaela Rumlová:** Funding acquisition, Resources, Supervision. **Jan Bartáček:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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